

A MACHINE LEARNING-BASED QUANTITATIVE STRUCTURE-ACTIVITY RELATIONSHIP STUDY FOR THE CARCINOGENIC ACTIVITY OF PHENYLETHYLAMINE

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ABSTRACT: The psychotomimetic activity of substituted phenethylamines as psychedelic drugs is predicted using a novel model. The structure-activity study was carried out using a quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) method, which took into account the molecular structures and activities of the intended phenethylamine derivatives. 118 different substituted phenethylamines with published psychotomimetic activity values are used in this research. The QSAR analysis was carried out using a hybrid approach that included a genetic algorithm for variable selection and multiple linear regression analysis. A quantum-chemical analysis using a semi-empirical approach was used to find a stable conformation and generate additional descriptors for the QSAR study. As a result, a number of models were developed, with the best predictive performance coming from a ten-variable model with $r^2 = 0.7428$ and $q^2_{LOO} = 0.6738$. A leave-one-out technique, external set, and y-scrambling methods were used to test the best model's robustness and predictability. With the external set, the model's predictive ability was proven, with $r^2_{ext} = 0.7365$. The developed model can be used to predict the psychotomimetic activity of newly synthesized and untested organic compounds.

Key words: QSAR, psychotomimetic activity, phenethylamine.

1. Introduction.

The construction of models that allow predicting their various properties of the structures of chemical compounds, predicting the quantitative characteristics of biological activity, carcinogenicity is carried out using the Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR). QSAR is often used extensively to refer to various structure-property models [1].

The search for quantitative structure-property relationships is based on the use of methods of mathematical statistics and machine learning to build models that allow, by describing the structures of chemical compounds, to predict their properties (physical, chemical, biological activity). When predicting properties at the qualitative level (for example, whether a given chemical compound will have a given type of biological activity), they talk about solving a classification problem, whereas when predicting numerical values of properties, they talk about solving a regression problem [2].

The role of the structure of chemical mutagens in the efficiency of induction of certain genetic changes has been studied virtually since the discovery of chemical mutagenesis [3]. The study of the relationship between the structure of a chemical compound and the biological activity, it exhibits (in particular, mutagenic) is based on the basic proposition of the structural theory of chemistry, which states that the chemical structure determines the basic physicochemical properties of a given compound. This provision served as the basis for isolating certain factors (descriptors) in chemical compounds and establishing a connection, qualitative (SAR) or quantitative (QSAR), between them and the biological activity of the compound [4]. As such descriptors, various characteristics of the molecule are used: topological, quantum parameters and parameters related to the whole molecule.

The impetus for the application of the methodology, in relation to genotoxicity, SAR and QSAR were the ideas developed in the late 70s by Miller and Miller [5] about the decisive role of electrophilicity in the ability of chemical compounds to

react with DNA and induce mutagenesis and carcinogenesis. Based on this concept, Ashby introduced the concept of "structural alert", which is a structural signal of danger in the molecules of chemical compounds. Ashby and Tennan [6] sampled the most common electrophilic groups in genotoxicant molecules – "structural alerts" – and combined them into a hyperstructural molecule. By comparing this hypothetical molecule with the molecules of compounds for which genotoxic properties need to be predicted, it is possible to identify the presence of "structural alerts" in these compounds. Then, therefore, such compounds can be considered potential mutagens and carcinogens. The prognostic significance of an estimate based on the presence or absence of alerts in the molecule is close .

But if "structural alerts" show only the potential for a molecule to exhibit genotoxic activity, then possible modulators of biological activity reduce or increase this potential. Such modulators can be reactivity, solubility of the compound, the existence of specific metabolic sites. Moreover, during the analysis, one should not confuse the functions of "structural alerts" responsible for activity with the functions of modulators, which can lead to false predictions.

The determination of the set of descriptors for each molecule, their correlations with mutagenic carcinogenic activity, the selection of the most significant descriptors that make the greatest contribution to biological activity, require the use of special computer programs. The most promising from the point of view of predicting genotoxicity can be considered the packages of programs CASE, MULTICASE, META [8-10].

Fig.1. Graphical representation of statistical characteristics of models observed by the Predicted Correlation Graph.

Fig.2. Graphical representation of statistical characteristics of models according to williams graph

Fig.1-2 shows that QSAR is a good tool for non-experimental prediction, the values of all compounds are within the applicable range.

Currently, data are available for the analysis of almost all major groups of chemical compounds from alkylating agents to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons [11-13]. It is too early to talk about the well-known equations describing the dependence of mutagenic activity on the structure of certain classes of chemical compounds. However, the available evidence suggests that the QSAR methodology can be successfully used for extra-experimental prediction of the activity of new compounds if they belong to a particular series of chemical compounds for which QSAR equations already exist. This is of great importance in establishing the order, and in some cases the depth, of experimental research.

2. Methods.

A specific QSAR modeling techniques used in this study [3]. The dataset of the compounds for the present research work was collected from several published

experimental data [6-7] with psychotomimetic activity (PA). All original activity data were converted into molar $1/\log(\text{PA})$ response variables.

3. Result and Discussion.

The whole set of 118 compounds was divided into the training set consisted of 98 compounds and a test set (predicting set) of 20 compounds. GA-MLRA technique has identified several models.

The following equation represent the developed model towards the PA:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Log(PA)} = & 0.4937 (\pm 0.3728) \mathbf{Jhetv} - 0.0315 (\pm 0.0157) \mathbf{MPC07} - 0.8057 \\ & (\pm 0.4383) \mathbf{MATS8v} - 0.2671 (\pm 0.2819) \mathbf{GATS5e} + 11.0819 (\pm 4.0085) \\ & \mathbf{BELm1} + 1.0233 (\pm 0.4618) \quad \mathbf{BEHe8} \ 3.1745 (\pm 1.3014) \mathbf{E2m} - 0.5801 (\pm 13.8738) \\ & \mathbf{R6u} + 10.8007 (\pm 5.1876) \mathbf{R4p} + 0.1922 (\pm 0.1824) \mathbf{H-051} - 19.1914 (\pm 7.7205) \end{aligned}$$

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